

CHARACTERIZATION AND GAS SENSING PROPERTIES OF GRAPHENE NANORIBBONS/ INDIUM TRIOXIDE /POLYANILINE NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this study, graphene nanoribbons (GNR) were prepared by longitudinal unzipping of multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs). Graphene nanoribbons (GNR)-indium trioxide (In_2O_3) hybrid materials were prepared by a solvothermal reaction of an indium precursor containing GNR. Finally, the graphene nanoribbons/indium trioxide/polyaniline (GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI) composite was prepared by in-situ polymerization method for ammonia detection. The synthesized hybrid nanocomposites were characterized by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), X-ray diffraction (XRD) and Transmission electron microscopy (TEM). In ammonia gas sensing, the addition of mesoporous In_2O_3 nanoparticles and GNR can significantly improve the sensing performance as compared to that of pure PANI. This result indicated that the GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI sensor showed highest response value of 21.9 at 4 ppm NH_3 at room temperature, which was about 2.7 times higher than that of pure PANI. The enhancement of sensing performance for the GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI nanocomposite was attributed to synergistic effect of p-n junction of PANI and mesoporous In_2O_3 nanoparticles with high surface ratio.

1 INTRODUCTION

Since the beginning of industrial revolution, humans have been exploiting the natural resources on a large scale which has led to pollution. Toxic gases, such as ammonia (NH_3), nitrogen dioxide (NO_2), carbon monoxide (CO), hydrogen sulphide (H_2S) and hydrocarbons cause adverse impact on living organisms. Among these, NH_3 is a color-less, stimulating, toxic and flammable gas, which mainly comes from industrial processes, biological metabolism and automobile exhaust [1]. Gas sensors are considered to be useful tools in the prevention of air pollution, because they can give us some advise in advance. Therefore, it is necessary to build up low cost, highly sensitive, reliable and reproducible NH_3 gas sensor systems operated at room temperature. Indium oxide (In_2O_3), a kind of n-type semiconductor with a wide band gap (ca. 3.6 eV) [2], is a fascinating material for its extensive applications in gas sensor, biosensors, solar cells [3]. Up to now, In_2O_3 and In_2O_3 -based composites acting as gas sensors have been investigated by many researchers due to their outstanding physical and chemical properties. The disadvantage of In_2O_3 is its high operating temperature (350-450 °C) which limits its real time applications. Polyaniline (PANI) a typical conductive polymer, has controllable conductivity and can be used to work at room temperature [4]. This is a significant advantage compared with metal oxides sensors, which will be used at several hundred degrees Celsius. However, the stability of polyaniline thin films need to be improved for sensor application. This phenomenon is associated with the deprotonation on air and the poor charge transport between the polymer chains of PANI [5]. One possible solution to this issue is the use of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) in order to increase the charge transport on these films. Thus, the combination of stability and high conductivity of carbon nanotubes with the high reactivity of polyaniline films is a promising solution to achieve better results for gas sensor applications. Graphene nanoribbons (GNR), another type of carbon material, were prepared by longitudinal unzipping of multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs). Compared with CNT, GNR has a large specific surface area and is in contact with ammonia. So in this work, we report a high performance ammonia gas sensor based on GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI nanocomposite

prepared by a simple, low-cost, in-situ oxidative polymerization method and solvothermal reaction. The as-prepared GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI nanocomposite was fully investigated using XRD, TEM and FTIR. The sensing performances of the GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI nanocomposite were determined at room temperature.

2 EXPERIMENT

Graphene nanoribbons were prepared by longitudinal unzipping of multi-walled carbon nanotubes [6]. GNR/ In_2O_3 hybrids were prepared by a solvothermal reaction of an indium precursor containing GNR. Finally, GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI was prepared by in-situ polymerization method for ammonia detection (Fig.1).

Fig 1: The preparation process of GNR / In_2O_3 / PANI hybrid nanocomposites.

2.1 Preparation of graphene nanoribbons

Graphene nanoribbons was synthesized by longitudinal unzipping of multi-walled carbon nanotubes. Briefly, MWCNTs (0.1 g) was added into 100 mL of 98% H_2SO_4 solution and treated with ultrasonic wave for 30 min. Then, the solution was stirred for 2 h. Thereafter, 0.5 g of potassium permanganate was added to the above mixed solution and stirred for another 2 h at 85°C . The solution was added to 500 mL of 5% H_2O_2 and precipitated for 24 hours. The product was washed with deionized water and ethanol alternately for several times, and dried at oven of 65°C for 8 h.

2.2 Synthesis of graphene nanoribbons(GNR)/indium trioxide (In_2O_3) hybrid materials

Indium (III) nitrate hydrate (0.028 g), GNR (9.2 mg) and glycerol (1.1 mL) were dissolved into IPA (32 mL) and sonicated for 10 min. The mixture was transferred to a Teflon-lined stainless autoclave, which was kept at 180°C for 6 h. The black precipitate was collected and washed with ethanol four times and dried at 70°C for 12 h. After calcination at 500°C for 2 h, GNR-In-glycerates were transformed into GNR- In_2O_3 hybrid materials.

2.3 Synthesis of GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI nanocomposites

The GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI nanocomposite was fabricated by using in-situ polymerization technique. Aniline (0.17 ml) was dissolved in 10 ml HCl (1 M), and then 0.07g GNR/ In_2O_3 was added into the aniline solution; And then, APS (0.002 mol) hydrochloric acid solution was dropwise added into the GNR/ In_2O_3 /aniline mixture as the oxidant and kept in-situ chemical oxidative polymerization reaction in an ice-water bath for 2 h. The dark green precipitate was collected and washed with ethanol several times and dried at 60°C for 12 h.

2.4 Gas-sensing measurement by home-made test system

The ammonia gas sensing measurement shown in Fig 2 were performed by a home-made test system. The sensor was fixed in a test chamber and the dry NH_3 gas and N_2 is used as the balance gas. The real-time resistance changes of sensors were measured and recorded by a Keysight 34461A data acquisition system.

Fig 2: Schematic illustration of home-made gas sensing test system.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Morphology of GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI nanocomposites

The XRD diffraction data of PANI, In_2O_3 , GNR, GNR/ In_2O_3 and GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI samples were shown in Fig 3. For the pure GNR, the diffraction peak at 10.5° is due to the (001) crystal plane of the GNR layer structure. The diffraction peaks of In_2O_3 are observed at $2\theta = 21.5^\circ, 30.6^\circ, 35.5^\circ, 45.7^\circ, 51.0^\circ$ and 60.7° , which correspond to the (211), (222), (400), (431), (440) and (622) planes of the In_2O_3 [3]. The X-ray diffraction peak of GNR/ In_2O_3 hybrid shows similar tendency of the In_2O_3 , In_2O_3 nanoparticle/GNR indicating that the In_2O_3 nanoparticles exist in the hybrid material. The XRD pattern of PANI shows three prominent peak at $2\theta = 14.7^\circ, 20.5^\circ$ and 25.1° , which are consistent with the (011), (020), and (200) planes [7]. Wide diffraction peaks between 10° and 30° can be observed in the XRD patterns of PANI, which are due to the parallel and perpendicular periodicity of the polymer (PANI) chain. For the GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI nanocomposite, the diffraction peak of In_2O_3 nanoparticle disappear, which indicates that PANI was coated the surface of GNR/ In_2O_3 hybrid.

The functional groups of samples were measured using FTIR spectra, as shown in Fig.4. The peak at 1720 cm^{-1} for the GNR was attributed to the C=O stretching vibration; it indicates the existence of oxidized functional groups in the GNR. For the pure In_2O_3 nanoparticles, three main peaks appeared at $605, 565, \text{ and } 535\text{ cm}^{-1}$; were attributed to the typical characterization peaks of In_2O_3 cubic structure. The In_2O_3 nanoparticle/GNR nanocomposite is observed, and the appearances of the peaks 605 cm^{-1} of the In_2O_3 nanoparticles reveal that the In_2O_3 nanoparticles exist in the GNR matrix. We can clearly observe that PANI has several FTIR characteristic absorption peaks. The peak at 1562 cm^{-1} and 1477 cm^{-1} corresponded to the C=C and C=N stretch of quinoid rings and benzenoid structure of PANI. The peak at 1296 cm^{-1} is assigned to C-N stretching mode of benzenoid unit, and the peaks at 798 cm^{-1} are attributed to the C-H out-of-plane bending vibration of the benzene ring. The major peaks pertained to PANI can be observed in the FTIR spectrum of GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI samples. In addition, a peak isn't appeared at $550\text{-}650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the FTIR spectrum of GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI composite is due to the PANI evenly coated the surface. This result was consistent with the XRD analysis.

Fig 3: The XRD pattern of GNR, In_2O_3 , $\text{GNR}/\text{In}_2\text{O}_3$, PANI and $\text{GNR}/\text{In}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PANI}$.

Fig 4: The FTIR spectrum of GNR, In_2O_3 , $\text{GNR}/\text{In}_2\text{O}_3$, PANI and $\text{GNR}/\text{In}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PANI}$.

Fig 5: The TEM images of (a) In_2O_3 nanoparticle, (b) $\text{GNR}/\text{In}_2\text{O}_3$ hybrid and, (c) $\text{GNR}/\text{In}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PANI}$ nanocomposite.

The morphologies of the In_2O_3 nanoparticles, $\text{GNR}/\text{In}_2\text{O}_3$ hybrid and $\text{GNR}/\text{In}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PANI}$ nanocomposite were observed using TEM; they can be seen in Fig 5. Figure 5(a) shows the pure In_2O_3 nanoparticles with diameters of approximately 70-100 nm. In the $\text{GNR}/\text{In}_2\text{O}_3$ hybrid (Fig 5(b)), it can be observed that the In_2O_3 nanoparticles are well loaded on the GNR surface. This result demonstrates that there is a good interaction between the In_2O_3 nanoparticles and the GNR. In addition, the In_2O_3 average particles size decreased about 20-70 nm. From the image of the $\text{GNR}/\text{In}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PANI}$ nanocomposite (Fig. 5c), it can be observed that the PANI (black arrow) was coated the surface of the

nanocomposite. Moreover, it can be seen that the In_2O_3 nanoparticles (red arrow) are present in the nanocomposite.

3.2 Ammonia-sensing properties

Fig 6(a) shows the dynamic response-recovery curves of the pure PANI and GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI sensors upon exposure of 4 ppm ammonia at room temperature. The GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI nanocomposite highest response of 21.9 at 4 ppm NH_3 , which is more than 2.7 times higher than that of pure PANI. Moreover, the sensor based on GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI exhibited good reproducibility to 4 ppm NH_3 at room temperature by performing three reversible cycles, as shown in Fig 6(b).

Fig 6: (a) Dynamic response-recovery curves of pure PANI and GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI, (b) The repeatability of GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI. (4ppm NH_3 at room temperature)

The room temperature dynamic gas response investigation of GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI nanocomposite sensor towards 2.1-5.7 ppm concentration of NH_3 gas was shown in Fig 7(a). The dynamic response curve indicates that the as increase response of sensor with increasing NH_3 gas concentration. In addition, the response-concentration fitting curves of sensors towards NH_3 are shown in Fig 7(b). It could be seen that the good linear characteristics of GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI sensors are obtained.

Fig 7: The (a) dynamic response curves, and (b) response-concentration fitting curves of GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI thin film sensors toward 2.1-5.7 ppm NH_3 at room temperature.

3.3 Sensing mechanism

It can be observed that the GNR/In₂O₃/PANI nanocomposite sensor has excellent ammonia gas sensing properties at room temperature from above experimental results, suggesting the GNR/In₂O₃/PANI nanocomposite is an outstanding candidate material for ammonia detection. The potential ammonia-sensing mechanism is attributed to the synergistic effect of the ternary nanomaterial and special interactions at p-n heterojunction. During the sensing process, GNR/In₂O₃/PANI ternary thin film is exposed to electron-donating NH₃, and NH₃ molecules would donate electrons to PANI. In this case, the holes concentration in PANI backbone is reduced resulting in a transformation of PANI from emeraldine salt (ES) to emeraldine base (EB) and the decrease of film conductivity [8]. Furthermore, the experimental results (Fig 6) illustrated that sensors based on GNR/In₂O₃/PANI possessed better sensing performance than that of pure PANI. The improved sensing properties were attributed to the effect of In₂O₃. This result can be contributed to the formation of p-n hetero junction at the surface between p-type PANI and n-type In₂O₃. On the other hand, the PANI was coated on the surface of mesoporous In₂O₃ nanoparticles to form core-shell hybrid structure, which a depletion layer was formed at the interface due to the neutralization of electrons in the In₂O₃ and holes in PANI. Finally, the p-n heterojunction in equilibrium and the depletion layer was narrow, which means a wide conductive path. when the hybrid was placed to NH₃ atmosphere, NH₃ captured the protons of the acidified polyaniline. and destroyed the original equilibrium state. In this case, the depletion region was widened and conductive path was narrowed resulting in the increase of hybrid resistance [9]. Then, the addition of GNR reduces the In₂O₃ particles from 70-120 nm to 50-70 nm, resulting in an increase in specific surface area. The large specific surface area of GNR/In₂O₃/PANI further increases the contact sites with PANI, which can provide a great deal of adsorption sites for ammonia gas.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In summary, the enhanced room temperature NH₃ sensor based on GNR/In₂O₃/PANI nanocomposite prepared through combination methods of facile solvothermal reaction and in-situ chemical oxidative polymerization was developed. The sensing performances of sensors based on pure PANI and PANI/In₂O₃ nanoparticles/GNR nanocomposite to NH₃ at room temperature were tested and the results demonstrated that the sensor based on GNR/In₂O₃/PANI nanocomposite showed the best sensing performance at room temperature. The response value of the GNR/In₂O₃/PANI nanocomposite sensor to 4 ppm NH₃ was 21.9 at room temperature and exhibited 2.7 times higher than those of pure PANI sensors. The improved sensing performance was attributed to synergistic effect of p-n junction of PANI and In₂O₃ nanoparticles and the large specific surface area. The GNR/In₂O₃/PANI nanocomposite was found to be a good candidate to constructing high-performance ammonia gas sensor with the advantages of low cost and room temperature detection.

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